

The Implementation of Feature Selection Techniques in Search for Diagnostic Criteria for Epilepsy

S. A. Demin*

*Institute of Physics, Kazan Federal University,
18 Kremlevskaya Str, Kazan, 420008 Tatarstan, RUSSIA*

V. A. Yunusov

*Institute of Computational Mathematics and Information Technologies,
Kazan Federal University, 18 Kremlevskaya Str, Kazan, 420008 Tatarstan, RUSSIA*

A. V. Minkin

*Yelabuga Institute, Kazan Federal University,
18 Kremlevskaya Str, Kazan, 420008 Tatarstan, RUSSIA*

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In this study, we consider possible application of feature selection methods implemented in the Weka software package for the diagnosis of epilepsy. We analyze bioelectric brain signals for solving the problem of classifying electroencephalograms obtained from two groups of people: patients with epilepsy and healthy subjects. Features were extracted from electroencephalograms using Python framework EEGlib, which is compatible with Weka package. During the analysis, we considered 11 machine learning algorithms included in the Weka package, for which the mean value of classification F score exceeded 0.8 and mean value of $AUC ROC$ reached 0.89 on the original feature space (28 features for classification). Analysis was performed in two stages. At the first stage, we analyzed signals recordings under study using classifying machine learning methods within the initial feature space. After that, we used two evaluators: CfsSubsetEval and WrapperSubsetEval and chose new subset of features of each evaluator based on individual predictive power of features. Then, we trained classifying algorithms on obtained subsets of features for evaluating their effectiveness for solving classification problem. Feature evaluators increased the average F score and $AUC ROC$ of most methods but decreased for those with high values. Best result was obtained for Random Forest algorithm without feature selection and the F score, and $AUC ROC$ of this approach was 0.882 and 0.965 correspondingly.

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1. Introduction

Time series of experimental biomedical data, including electroencephalogram recordings (EEG), are now widely used for the task of determining diagnostic criteria for neurological diseases [1]. One of the most common neurological diseases is epilepsy, characterized by seizures

associated with impaired brain function [2]. EEG signal recordings are widely used now by researchers for studying bioelectrical activity of human brain. To study EEG, a variety of methods are now used: auto- and cross-correlation analysis [3], fractal analysis [4], time-frequency synchronization [5] and other methods.

But due to the personal diversity of human health parameters it is very difficult to properly interpret physiological statistical

*E-mail: serge_demin@mail.ru

parameters. To solve this issue, machine learning and deep learning methods are now actively being developed and implemented for detection of pathological brain activity. For example, in work [6] authors used convolutional neural network (CNN) for epilepsy diagnosis. Authors implemented 13 layers CNN and achieved 88.67% accuracy.

In other work [7] authors used combination of 7 classifiers with one of the feature selection methods: recursive feature elimination in the task of automatic seizure diagnosis. The authors reduced set of features from 11 to 8 features and achieved accuracy of 99%.

In addition, the same task was considered in paper [8], in which 6 feature selection methods were implemented in combination with 9 classifiers. Feature selection techniques were evaluated to rank and reduce original set of features (over 700 features) and selecting 20 or 25 features with the most predictive power. Although the accuracy of classification task increased for all feature selection methods (from approximately 70% to over 90%), none of these methods outperformed the rest of them due to the dependency on feature set and classifier model.

In our work, we use a set of different machine learning techniques to predict whether considered EEG signal recording belongs to patient with epilepsy or to control subject, and then establish statistical parameters (features) with the biggest impact on this prediction. The purpose of this work is not only to apply machine learning methods for diagnosing epilepsy using machine learning models, but also to find the optimal set of statistical characteristics using two methods of feature estimators.

2. Materials and methods

Machine learning is one of the new and actively developing methods of analysis, combining approaches that can “learn” based on the received data, which allows you to perform a wide range of different tasks. Machine

learning can be used to solve problems of detection, prediction, recognition, diagnostics, and optimization. In the area of physics of complex biological systems machine learning methods are widely used in the study of structure and for analysis of the dynamic behavior: forecasting of the future evolution and establishing a causal relationship. Machine learning approach allows establishing hidden trends in data, which are hard to obtain using traditional statistical methods.

Data analysis and machine learning software package Weka [9] was used for classifier training and for the following feature selection. The feature selection procedure in Weka package involves the combined use of an attribute estimator and a search method. An attribute estimator is a method by which each feature is evaluated in the context of a target variable. A search method is a method by which a feature space is searched to find a suitable subset of features.

In our study we use the CfsSubsetEval and WrapperSubsetEval attribute subset evaluators. Attribute evaluators estimate the worth of a subset of attributes by considering the individual predictive ability of each feature along with the degree of redundancy between them. Then the feature subset only with strong correlation with the target class is obtained [10]. After that, the effectiveness of the obtained subset is evaluated using different classification algorithms.

Experimental data were obtained in the course of the international cooperation program [11].

The data files were background EEG signals recorded from the cerebral cortex for two groups of men:

- 8 patients with epilepsy;
- 9 healthy (control) subjects with no neurological diseases.

All subjects in resting state with closed eyes during biomedical data recording. Recording was carried out with 19 scalp electrodes arranged in accordance with the standard “10-20%”

FIG. 1. International scheme of electrodes layout “10-20%”.

international electrode placement system (Figure 1) with a sampling frequency of 200 Hz and about 20 seconds long each.

The limited amount of data under consideration is due to the fact that this work represents the first step in the classification of EEG signals in normal and pathological conditions. The purpose of this work is to determine the statistical parameters of signals with the highest predictive power for subsequent consideration of large samples of experimental data.

As part of data preprocessing using EEGlib framework for each EEG record, i.e., for each electrode, a set of statistical indicators was calculated: Hjort parameters (activity, complexity, and mobility), power of α -, β -, θ - and δ -activity of the cerebral cortex, analysis of fluctuations without a trend (DFA), Higuchi fractal dimension, Lempel-Ziv complexity, Petrosian’s fractal dimension and sample entropy. These parameters are representative features of EEG recordings and are widely used.

3. Results and discussion

The analysis was carried out in two stages: at the first stage, 11 machine learning techniques included in the Weka software package were implemented for the task of classification of epileptic signals recordings. Each recording for each electrode was considered as a single independent observation. Thus, the number of instances reached 272. Due to the small size of the data set under consideration, the sample division was carried out using stratified cross-validation with division into 5 blocks, which emulates the presence of a test sample.

A variety of machine approaches are increasingly used for this task. All models were trained on the original feature space with 28 features for classification. The original set of features included widely used statistical parameters such as: Hjort activity, Hjort complexity, Hjort mobility, δ -power, θ -power, α -power, β -power, detrended fluctuation analysis parameter, Higuchi fractal dimension, Lempel-Ziv Complexity, Petrosian fractal dimension, sample entropy and also an ID of electrode from which the signal was recorded, using one-hot encoding procedure. The highest F score was for the Random Forest, Bagging, and KStar methods and exceeded 0.874. Accuracy ($F \times 100\%$) of all machine learning algorithms are shown on Figure 2.

At the second stage of the experiment, the feature selection technique was implemented to reduce feature space size using two different methods. First method included CfsSubsetEval attribute evaluator in a combination with GreedyStepwise search method. Second method included WrapperSubsetEval attribute evaluator in a combination with the Random Forest Classifier and the GreedyStepwise search method.

Using CfsSubsetEval attribute evaluator, we established the most important features for the following classification of EEG signals recordings: Hjort activity, Petrosian Fractal Dimension and Sample Entropy. While using WrapperSubsetEval, following features were the

FIG. 2. (Color online) Accuracy of classifiers without any feature selection techniques.

most meaningful for the task of classification: Hjort activity, Petrosian Fractal Dimension and Sample Entropy, θ -power and Lempel-Ziv Complexity.

Then classification models were trained again on the subsets of features obtained by two attribute evaluators. The results are shown on Figure 3 ($F \times 100\%$).

Comparison of the values of F score results of classifiers with and without feature selection shows that for some of the applied methods F score improves, while for others it decreases (see Table 1).

For the methods with the highest value of F score (Random Forest, Bagging, AdaBoostM1 and KStar) it decreases after implementation of each of feature selection techniques. For both feature evaluators F score of machine learning algorithms with the lowest F score increases. In average, F score of all algorithms improved. As a result, average F score of all algorithms is increased by 0.018 for both subset evaluators, and, therefore, implementation of feature selection technique was successful.

FIG. 3. (Color online) Accuracy of classifiers using different feature selection techniques.

The same is true for the $AUC ROC$ metric (Table 2). The highest value of this metric is for the Random Forest algorithm and mean value when using subset evaluators is increased by 0.013.

4. Conclusions

The unique properties of complex systems are fully reflected in the processes taking place in the human brain. A complex systems is a system consisting of many components, the interaction between which leads to the emergence of qualitatively new emergent properties. The study of the basic laws of the organization and functioning of neurons and neural formations is of particular importance for neurosciences: neurobiology, neuroengineering, neuroinformatics, as well as artificial intelligence and big data

Table 1. F score of classifiers with different feature selection techniques. NFS is short cut for No Feature Selection, CSE is for CfsSubsetEval, WSE is for WrapperSubsetEval.

Classifier model	F score		
	NFS	CSE	WSE
Random Forest	0.882	0.849	0.853
LogitBoost	0.853	0.838	0.849
Bagging	0.874	0.871	0.856
AdaBoostM1	0.856	0.845	0.845
KStar	0.874	0.864	0.874
Simple Logistic	0.798	0.827	0.812
SGD	0.761	0.802	0.812
Multilayer Perceptron	0.75	0.836	0.837
Logistic	0.819	0.827	0.819
Naive Bayes	0.738	0.815	0.817
Bayes Net	0.796	0.831	0.827

Table 2. $AUC ROC$ for classifiers with different feature selection techniques.

Classifier model	$AUC ROC$		
	NFS	CSE	WSE
Random Forest	0.965	0.939	0.931
LogitBoost	0.932	0.922	0.92
Bagging	0.931	0.918	0.911
AdaBoostM1	0.933	0.923	0.923
KStar	0.958	0.93	0.93
Simple Logistic	0.877	0.894	0.893
SGD	0.76	0.801	0.812
Multilayer Perceptron	0.833	0.905	0.904
Logistic	0.896	0.907	0.906
Naive Bayes	0.83	0.887	0.876
Bayes Net	0.858	0.911	0.887

sciences. Physiological research data serve as source material for mathematical modelling, the development of computer software tools and the creation of intelligent analytical systems.

Epilepsy is a neurological disease that leads to the manifestation of seizure of its patients. The analysis of bioelectric brain signals recordings – electroencephalograms is widely used in the field of neurology for diagnosis this pathology.

In this work, we implemented machine learning methods in combination with feature selection techniques included in Weka software package. We calculated a set of statistical features for EEG signals of people with epilepsy and without it (control group). Then we carried out the task of classification for these two groups of subjects.

Using the original feature space (28 features) we established algorithms with the highest F score and $AUC ROC$: Random Forest, Bagging and KStar models. Then we obtained two subsets of features using two feature evaluators: CfsSubsetEval attribute evaluator in a combination with GreedyStepwise and WrapperSubsetEval in combination with Random Forest method with GreedyStepwise search method. The goal of reduction of feature space was to leave under consideration only features with the highest predictive power for a possible increase in F score and $AUC ROC$. As a result, feature evaluators in average increased values of F score and $AUC ROC$ of all methods by 1% (in some cases up to 6%) but decreased for the ones with highest F score and $AUC ROC$ metrics. And, finally, the highest F score and $AUC ROC$ were obtained for the Random Forest without using any feature evaluators: 0.882 and 0.965 correspondingly.

We believe that our study, after appropriate validation, will be helpful for the development and application of the new diagnostic methods for the patients with epilepsy. The efficiency of classification of the considered experimental data may be increased after hyperparameter optimization for all the used machine learning algorithms [12–14], and by parameter set extension: for example, including a variety of fractal [15–17], correlation parameters [18, 19] or statistical memory measures in the framework of Memory Functions Formalism [20–22].

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